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Demonstrating large pit thermal energy storages and improving their components, processes, and procedures for an accelerated realisation of 100% sustainable district heating networks in Europe.

KPIs and KDPs in LTES systems

Relevance of KPIs and KDPs for different project phases

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

CAPEX	Capital expenditures
DH	District heating
DHN	District heating network
ES	Energy storage
GA	Grant agreement
IEA	International energy agency
KDP	Key design parameter
KI	Key indicator (KDPs and KPIs)
KPI	Key performance indicator
LCOH	Levelized cost of heat
LTES	Large thermal energy storage ¹
OPEX	Operational expenditures
TCP	Technology collaboration programme
TES	Thermal energy storage

¹ A large thermal energy storage is defined in IEA-ES Task 39 as a sensible thermal energy storage (no phase change), designed to store at least 1 GWh of heat per year at atmospheric pressure (no pressurized system). The stored heat should be suitable for discharge into DHN, at temperatures higher than 50°C (see https://iea-es.org/task-39/wp-content/uploads/sites/21/IEA-ES_Task39_WPA_Deliverable_A0a_Task_brochure%E2%80%93Introduction.pdf)

1. Introduction

This document summarizes the results of the evaluation done by the project partners of each TREASURE demonstrator-teams within Task 4.1 “Pre-simulation activities” rating the importance of numerous key performance indicators (KPIs) and key design parameters (KDPs) for a given project phase.

The definition of KPI and KDP is originally provided in Deliverable A4² is added here for ease of reading.

Key performance indicator (KPI): are defined as a value that can only be obtained after implementation, meaning that they require the storage to be operated. Those are monitoring data that are mainly used for characterizing the performance of the LTES, such as charged and discharge energies, energy efficiency or the heat supply tariff to the DHN consumers.

Key design parameter (KDP): are defined as a value that can be obtained before implementing the storage. Those are theoretical figures mainly used for the design and sizing of the LTES, such as the volume, the land area required or the storage capacity.

With these definitions in mind, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are quantifiable measures used to evaluate the performance of a system. They must be applicable across different systems and operational conditions to enable meaningful comparisons. In contrast, Key Design Parameters (KDPs) are the defining characteristics of a design that can be adjusted but do not provide direct evaluation; they simply describe how the system is.

In a Large Thermal Energy Storage (LTES) system, KDPs include design-related parameters such as dimensions, slope angle, temperature range, diffuser positioning, etc. These parameters are typically derived from design decisions and can often be directly extracted from design information or, in some cases, estimated (e.g., storage lifetime). These parameters shape the design but require KPI analysis such as energy efficiency, cost evaluation, etc. to assess the system performance. By iteratively refining KDPs based on KPI evaluations, the design and operation of the system can be optimized. Unlike KDPs, KPIs depend not only on the design but also on the specific operational conditions (e.g., heat losses, discharged heat, etc.), making them more complex to determine. Evaluating KPI estimates through simulations enables informed decision-making and system optimization before construction. To achieve this, project developers, researchers, and engineers rely on advanced modeling tools that provide access to key information to calculate KPIs (e.g., Levelized Cost of Heat).

The main aim of this evaluation is to provide clarity and transparency between the project partners on how each of them assesses LTES systems in different phases of the project, i.e. knowledge exchange. Furthermore, this information should serve as a basis for discussion on how to characterize and evaluate the demonstrators in later phases of TREASURE (Task 4.2 “Expected performance of the demonstrators”

² IEA-ES TCP Task 39. [Deliverable A4: Method to carry out an LTES project, important questions & KPIs - Subtask A main report. 20/10/2024.](#)

and Task 4.3 “Evaluation of future system integration concepts”) or for LTES projects in general for that matter, and potentially in future stages of the TREASURE project derive a list of common KPIs and KDPs.

2. Methodology

A list of KPIs and KDPs has been prepared using the deliverable A4² published by the IEA-ES TCP Task 39 “Large thermal energy storages for district heating” and discussions within the task team as a basis. The list of KPIs and KDPs is added at the end of the document, see Annex A: Description of KPIs and KDPs.

Then, a simple evaluation method has been defined and each project partner has been then asked to rate the importance of each KI³ for three different project phases: opportunity, design and operation. The selection and definition of the project phases is based on the definition given within the IEA-ES TCP Task 39 (see Deliverable A1⁴ of Subtask A “Application scenarios, assessment of concepts, integration aspects” for details). For the sake of completeness, a short description for the opportunity and design phase are retrieved from the original document⁴.

Opportunity phase: The main objective of this phase is to identify the technical and economic potential for an LTES application within a given context. Thus, a feasibility study is essential and shall be carried out to cover all necessary background data and investigate the possibilities for different storage applications (e.g., short-term, long-term, and multifunctional storage of heat and/or cold) and the available LTES technologies. In addition, an initial risk assessment, economic estimations, and the identification of potential business cases are part of this study.

Design phase: The design phase spans between the end of the opportunity and the start of the implementation. Its purpose is to remove barriers and de-risk the project to be able to implement it at a later stage. It includes all the studies (technical, economic, regulatory, etc.) required to be able to implement the project. The clarification of all those specific constraints can have a decisive impact on the LTES design and its technical and economic relevance. The LTES optimal size and geometry are established in this phase.

In regard of the evaluation method, the KIs are evaluated with a score from 0 to 4. The meaning of the score given is the following,

- (0): The KI is never used, and it is not of interest.
- (1): The KI is never used, but it could be considered, i.e. it can help evaluate and interpret the performance of the system.
- (2): The KI is normally used but has a secondary role.
- (3): The KI is always calculated and used to understand and optimize the system.

³ Key indicator (KI) is used for convenience in the document to refer to KPIs as well as KDPs. Notice that key performance indicators (KPIs) refer to relevant indicators that are calculated with help of measurements in a broad sense, i.e. from a system in operation or synthetic, e.g. from simulation results. On the contrary, key design parameters (KDPs) refer to indicators that are based (or calculated) with design information and there is no need for measurements or simulation data.

⁴ IEA-ES TCP Task 39. [Deliverable A1: Method to carry out an LTES project, important questions & KPIs - Subtask A main report](#). 17/10/2024.

(4): The KI is very important and used as a basis for decision-making, i.e. move from a current phase to the next one (e.g. from opportunity to design phase).

Be aware that there might be some mismatch between the results of the KI evaluation and the real relevance of the KIs. Two main reasons for this issue are,

- the evaluation is filled in by the project partners, which try their best to consider the view of the demo partners, but there might be still some differences.
- Because the different KIs are relevant for different situations, the planned demonstrator (Task 4.2) but also for variations of the demonstrator and or future projects/scenarios (Task 4.3), the evaluation naturally varies.

All in all, the results at this stage should be treated and interpreted accordingly, i.e. used primarily as a basis for discussion, trying to better understand each demonstrator team and focusing on overall trends rather than claim for an “universal” list of relevant KIs for LTES related projects.

3. Results and discussion

A tabular summary of KPI and KDP rating done for the three considered project phases can be consulted in the Annex B: KI evaluation results, go to page 22.

The discussion of the results for the operation phase is skipped completely. The following sections focus on the results obtained for the opportunity and design phases as these are the main phases being addressed by the demonstrator projects. The results are reviewed and discussed more carefully for these two phases.

3.1 Evaluation of KPIs and KDPs for the opportunity phase

For the opportunity phase, thirteen KIs yield an average score above or equal to 3.5, and thus these KIs are designated as very relevant for the early project phase opportunity. It is worth mentioning that among the KIs listed below, there is a noticeable divergence (above or equal to 2 points) in the scoring between demonstrators for three KPIs (highlighted in bold), see Table 1.

TABLE 1: LIST OF MOST RELEVANT KPIs FOR THE OPPORTUNITY PHASE.

KPI
Initial investment (TES CAPEX)
Initial investment (TES System CAPEX)
Annual charged heat
Annual discharged heat
TES System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed
Annual TES OPEX
Average energy costs of charging
Storage losses
Annual TES System OPEX
DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed

TABLE 2: LIST OF MOST RELEVANT KDPs FOR THE OPPORTUNITY PHASE.

KDP
Land required
Design storage temperature range
DHN Temperatures

The list of most relevant KIs includes...

- Economic decisive KPIs such as the investment needed for the project, for the TES itself and the rest of the system (post heating, ...).
- KDPs that strongly constrain the TES design and feasibility of the project such as space available/required and DHN temperatures.
- Meaningful KPIs to characterize the TES operation such as charged/discharged heat, storage temperature range, storage heat losses, and annual OPEX (TES and system).
- All the above KIs contain part of the information required to calculate the KPI levelized cost of heat (LCOH), which is widely used for benchmarking and comparing purposes. This KPI is rated important both at TES System level as well as on DH level.

The evaluation of the KPIs “Annual TES OPEX” and the “Annual TES System OPEX” for the different demonstrators are listed below, see Table 3.

TABLE 3: EVALUATION FOR EACH DEMONSTRATOR FOR THE KPIs “ANNUAL TES OPEX” AND “ANNUAL TES SYSTEM OPEX”.

KPI (project phase(s))	Rostock (DE)	Pau (FR)	Pancevo (RS)	Wien (AT)	Choszczno (PL)	Hechingen (DE)
Annual TES OPEX (opportunity)	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	2,0
Annual TES System OPEX (opportunity)	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	2,0

The relatively low score for TES and TES System OPEX by Hechingen can be attributed the main project goal, which is to design an economically feasible system with a high share of renewable energy and low CO₂ emissions, or in other words, a balanced system in terms of economics and environmental aspects. In this regard, KPIs that account different economic aspects such LCOH become much more important than specific OPEX. Furthermore, as during the evaluation the DH system is considered completely, in case heat from the DH system is being charged into the LTES, the associated cost will not be included in the OPEX as this has been already accounted for at the heat source(s).

The third KPI with some divergence in the scoring is the “DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH)”, see Table 4.

TABLE 4: EVALUATION FOR EACH DEMONSTRATOR FOR THE KPI “DH SYSTEM LEVELIZED COST OF HEAT (LCOH)”.

KPI (project phase(s))	Rostock (DE)	Pau (FR)	Pancevo (RS)	Wien (AT)	Choszczno (PL)	Hechingen (DE)
DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed (opportunity and design)	4,0	4,0	1,0	4,0	4,0	4,0

The reasoning behind the low score by Pancevo is explained by the fact that the system under consideration is a relatively independent system (TES + Solar thermal installation + post heating unit) with no heat being charged from the DH network, so that the view while evaluating the KPIs shifts to a more project-oriented view, where the LCOH of the TES (and TES system) are the most relevant KPIs, and work with a target-value for the LCOH of the TES system is considered enough.

From the discussions about these KPIs the following can be highlighted. The performance of the overall system has priority over parts of the system. How this is considered, might vary among partners, from project to project, and based on experience. Though it can be hardly generalized the bottom line might be that the approach followed should be reasonable and should facilitate the obtention of key performance indicators (KPIs) to support decision-making. An exemplary reasoning would be that when dealing with a small system with reduced impact or interaction with the existing system, the focus can be placed primarily on the new (local) system if preferred. Conversely, for large systems with strong interaction with the existing system, do require a more systemic approach.

Looking further down on the KI list, in the range of an average score between 3,5 and 3, we get a list of some additional relevant KPIs and KDPs,

TABLE 5: LIST OF RELEVANT KPIs FOR THE OPPORTUNITY PHASE.

KPI
Number of heat storage cycles per year
Energy consumption of the post heating unit(s)
Energy sources mix of the overall system
Energy specific CO2 emissions with or without LTES
TES Energy efficiency
Heat provided sorted by technology
Specific TES CAPEX

TABLE 6: LIST OF RELEVANT KDPs FOR THE OPPORTUNITY PHASE.

KDP
Storage lifetime
Design storage capacity
Storage height / depth
Charge and discharge capacity (Max or averaged e.g. annually)
Maturity of the solution
Distance to DHN

No major deviations are worth mentioning, all demo partners evaluated the above KIs in the range from 2 to 4. In this upper-mid range we see KIs related to

- the technologies themselves, e.g. storage lifetime, maturity of the solution,
- the operation of the TES (and system), such as number of heat storage cycles per year, energy consumption for post heating.

In the middle range, i.e. KIs with an average score between 3 and 2,5 we find the following KIs,

TABLE 7: LIST OF KPIS WITH AVERAGE SCORE FOR THE OPPORTUNITY PHASE.

KPI
Min/max temperature for the discharge
Min/max return temperature (to the storage)
Actual heat production peak
Energy specific TES OPEX
Average avoided energy costs by discharging
TES' effects on surroundings
Annual DH System OPEX

TABLE 8: LIST OF KDPs WITH AVERAGE SCORE FOR THE OPPORTUNITY PHASE.

KDP
Installed capacity of the heat production units MW _{th}
Maturity of the technologies used
Storage slope

The above listed KIs, even if scored “average”, are still seen as relevant and need to be considered in preparation of the design phase. The rating of the three KIs above highlighted in bold show some strong deviations between some demonstrators, varying from (1) not important at all to (4) very important. We asked a few partners what their reasoning on each of these KIs is trying to better understand the score, i.e. gaining insights into the specific project point of view and usage of these KIs. The scores of each demonstrator for these three KIs are listed in Table 9.

TABLE 9: EVALUATION FOR EACH DEMONSTRATOR FOR THE KIs “MATURITY OF THE TECHNOLOGY USED”, “TES' EFFECTS ON SURROUNDINGS” AND “ANNUAL SYSTEM DH SYSTEM OPEX”.

KI (project phase(s))	Rostock (DE)	Pau (FR)	Pancevo (RS)	Wien (AT)	Choszczno (PL)	Hechingen (DE)
Maturity of the technology used (opportunity)	4,0	4,0	1,0	3,0	2,0	4,0
TES' effects on surroundings (opportunity)	3,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	1,0	3,0
Annual DH System OPEX (opportunity)	4,0	3,0	1,0	4,0	3,0	2,0

In regard of the “maturity of the technology used”, a low score is given by Pancevo, not because the KDP itself is not important but rather because the LTES project already considers mature technologies so that it is not considered relevant to track this KDP. A similar point of view is used to score the Polish case in Choszczno, where well known PTES designs and state of the art technologies are being considered.

The impact of the TES temperatures on its surroundings is considered relevant. The primary reason for Choszczno’s low score is that the project owners have not requested an in-depth review of this aspect, leading to a low value for this KPI during the evaluation. This is likely due to task prioritization, where other unresolved questions are being addressed first, and the effects of the TES on its surroundings are not a top priority during the opportunity phase.

Furthermore, notice that the KPI’s definition remains vague, the topic (effects of TES’ temperatures on the surroundings) is mentioned, but the method for evaluating it (precise KPI definition and level of detail) is not specified, thus leaving room for interpretation during the evaluation process. Various situations illustrate the influence of LTES temperature on its surroundings:

- It may affect the soil’s water content, potentially impacting soil stability.
- It can alter groundwater temperatures (if present), which, depending on applicable regulations, could be a critical issue for the project.

Ultimately, the significance of these KPIs is highly dependent on the specific case being considered and the project phase.

In regard of the KPI “Annual DH System OPEX”, for the Pancevo case the same explanation given above holds, where the focus lies on the optimization of the TES system rather than having to consider the DH system. Similarly, the explanation given above is also valid for the Hechingen case.

On the bottom of our evaluation (average score lower or equal to 2,5) we got the following KIs,

TABLE 10: LIST OF LESS RELEVANT KPIs FOR THE OPPORTUNITY PHASE.

KPI
Internal energy change
Efficiency of the post heating unit(s)
Auxiliary power consumption
Seasonal energy efficiency
Heat losses of the DHN
Levelized cost of energy storage (LCOES) *Simplified or detailed
Number of volume storage cycles per year
MIX number
Exergy related KPIs, e.g. Exergy efficiency

TABLE 11: LIST OF LESS RELEVANT KDPs FOR THE OPPORTUNITY PHASE.

KDP
Installed consumers capacity in MW _{th}
Design energy density

Listed here we have KIs that are very specific and detailed from a technical point of view (e.g. MIX number, energy density, exergy efficiency, etc.) and technology specific KPIs (e.g. efficiency of post heating unit(s), LCOES, heat losses of the DHN, etc.). Some of them are relevant but are already being considered in other more systemic KIs (e.g. LCOES is related to LCOH, and efficiency of post heating unit(s) is related to OPEX). Others such as installed consumer capacity and DHN heat losses are interesting from a context and overall design point of view, but do not need to be constantly evaluated.

The score given by all partners are quite consistent, with the most obvious difference for the seasonal energy efficiency, where Wien and Pancevo rated them with a high score, 4 and 3 respectively, see Table 12.

TABLE 12: EVALUATION FOR EACH DEMONSTRATOR FOR THE KPI “SEASONAL ENERGY EFFICIENCY”.

KPI (project phase(s))	Rostock (DE)	Pau (FR)	Pancevo (RS)	Wien (AT)	Choszczno (PL)	Hechingen (DE)
Seasonal energy efficiency (opportunity)	2,0	1,0	3,0	4,0	2,0	1,0

Notice that within the KI list, there is another KPI closely related to the energy efficiency, this is the “TES energy efficiency”. The “TES energy efficiency” has been rated higher with a 3,2 in average, see page 22. To understand the difference in scoring, it is relevant to recall their definition, and thus meaning.

“TES energy efficiency” $\eta_{1,2}$ is defined as the ratio between the discharged energy E_{dis} and the charged energy E_{cha} within a well-defined period, typically a year. The difference of the state of charge between the end and start of the period, ΔE_{st} , is taken into account either at the numerator (discharged energy) or the denominator (charged energy), see equation (1). The KPI indicates therefore what can be seen as the “actual” TES efficiency, i.e. based on the real/expected operation.

$$\eta_1 = \frac{E_{dis}}{(E_{cha} + \Delta E_{st})} \text{ or } \eta_2 = \frac{(E_{dis} - \Delta E_{st})}{E_{cha}} \quad (1)$$

The seasonal energy efficiency ($\eta_{seasonal,1}$) is defined as the ratio between the stored seasonal energy (E_{seas}) and the sum of the seasonal energy and the heat losses (E_{loss}), see equation (2). The stored seasonal energy E_{seas} can be calculated as the difference between the minimum and maximum energy content over one year or alternatively based on the design thermal energy capacity, i.e. based on mass content, specific heat capacity and design maximal and minimal temperatures.

$$\eta_{seasonal,1} = E_{seas} / (E_{seas} + E_{loss}) \quad (2)$$

An alternative definition is given by equation (3),

$$\eta_{seasonal,2} = 1 - E_{loss} / E_{seas} \quad (3)$$

Important to mention is that if this KPI is evaluated with monitoring data (not based on simulation results), heat losses are not directly measured and need to be inferred from an energy balance of the TES ($E_{loss} = E_{cha} - E_{cha} + \Delta E_{st}$). Furthermore, notice that the result obtained from the two definitions differ slightly to one another, see Figure 1. In this regard, mention that equation (3) is slightly preferred as it is meaning is closer to the fundamental definition of efficiency, i.e. ratio between useful output and input.

FIGURE 1: SEASONAL EFFICIENCY I AND II AS FUNCTION OF THE PERCENTAGE OF HEAT LOSS RESPECT TO SEASONAL STORED HEAT.

Thus, contrary to the TES energy efficiency, the seasonal energy efficiency quantifies the efficiency of the storage system as if it was solely used for seasonal heat storage. It rewards a complete charge and discharge of the storage. i.e. difference between high and low temperatures / energy content. For this reason, seasonal energy efficiency can also be seen as a measure of the TES's effectiveness in terms of its energy storage capacity, specifically its effective heat capacity.

In the case of Wien, the reason behind a high score for the seasonal energy efficiency is the demo team's interest in the TES technology for seasonal applications. Even though the pilot demonstrator will only be able to shift a limited amount of heat due to its relatively small size compared to the DH system heat needs, there is a general interest in this KPI in view of a later up-scaling of the solution.

For Pancevo, the relevance of the seasonal energy efficiency KPI is linked to the relation of this KPI with the storage temperatures. Temperatures are very important for the performance of the system, the solar thermal and heat pump. A strong charging and discharging of the TES will indicate the storage is being "well" used in regard of the operating temperatures and can therefore serve to evaluate the TES system design and operation.

Also worth discussing is the fact that even though project decisions are mostly based on economic criteria, there is an economic KPI at the bottom of the list, the levelized cost of energy storage (LCOES). There are a few aspects that may lead to this situation,

- First and most important, the LTES project involves more than the LTES itself, so that it makes sense to optimize the system as a whole and not merely the LTES. Economic KPIs to evaluate the TES (and DH) system are available and were rated as highly important.
- Even though the LTES is a central part of the system, and the economic KPI LCOES in e.g. EUR/MWh seems to be useful in this regard, the fact that temperatures are so important in LTES projects makes the use of this KPI difficult when storages that provide heat at different temperature levels are compared.

3.2 Evaluation of KPIs and KDPs for the design phase

The evaluation of the KI rating for the design phase, indicates that twenty-six KIs yield an average score above 3.5, and thus these KIs are relevant for most demo-teams at the design project phase.

TABLE 13: LIST OF MOST RELEVANT KPIs FOR THE DESIGN PHASE.

KPI
Annual charged heat
Annual discharged heat
Storage losses
Initial investment (TES CAPEX)
Initial investment (TES System CAPEX)
TES' effects on surroundings
Energy consumption of the post heating unit(s)
Energy sources mix of the overall system
TES System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed
TES Energy efficiency
Heat provided sorted by technology
Annual TES OPEX
Annual TES System OPEX
Average energy costs of charging
Min/max temperature for the discharge
Min/max return temperature (to the storage)
Actual heat production peak
DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed

TABLE 14: LIST OF MOST RELEVANT KDPs FOR THE DESIGN PHASE.

KDP
Land required
Storage lifetime
Storage height / depth
Storage slope
Charge and discharge capacity (Max or averaged e.g. annually)
Design storage temperature range
Distance to DHN
DHN Temperatures

Notice that the number of relevant (with high score) KIs has doubled with respect to the thirteen KIs of the opportunity phase. Among them there are up to 5 KDPs (three more than in the opportunity phase) highlighting that the specifics of the design (e.g. storage height, charge/discharge capacity, etc.) become more important and can be used to optimize the system (moving out of the energy concept discussion and focusing on the specific design). In general it can be summarized that the difference between opportunity and design phase is that “details” become important, so that more design and operational aspects need to be monitored and evaluated to be able to benchmark the project, and ultimately yield an optimized and successful project.

The newly added KIs (compared to the opportunity phase) in the list above are highlighted in bold. These KIs are clearly related to the project design (e.g. storage height, lifetime, ...) as well as the operation of the system (e.g. min/max temperature for the discharge, ...) and ultimately their impact on the TES performance (e.g. TES efficiency) and the DH system itself (e.g. energy source mix of the overall system).

It is worth mentioning, that the already discussed discrepancies for a few KPIs (“Annual TES OPEX”, “Annual TES System OPEX” and “DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed”) are still present.

Further noticeable discrepancies are related to the storage temperatures and the heat production peak, see Table 15. There is no doubt that the temperatures are key for all LTES related projects, and it is believed that the difference in the scores can be attributed to the subjectivity and limitations of the evaluation approach, as well as the specificity of each case.

TABLE 15: EVALUATION FOR EACH DEMONSTRATOR FOR THE KIS “MIN/MAX TEMPERATURE FOR THE DISCHARGE”, “MIN/MAX RETURN TEMPERATURE - TO THE STORAGE” AND “ACTUAL HEAT PRODUCTION PEAK”.

KI (project phase(s))	Rostock (DE)	Pau (FR)	Pancevo (RS)	Wien (AT)	Choszczno (PL)	Hechingen (DE)
Min/max temperature for the discharge (design)	4,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	3,0	4,0
Min/max return temperature - to the storage (design)	4,0	3,0	4,0	2,0	4,0	4,0
Actual heat production peak (design)	4,0	3,0	4,0	2,0	4,0	4,0

A list in the middle to upper range, with KPIs and KDPs with an average score between 3,5 and 2,5 is as follows,

TABLE 16: LIST OF RELEVANT KPIs FOR THE DESIGN PHASE.

KPI
Number of heat storage cycles per year
Energy specific CO ₂ emissions with or without LTES
Energy specific TES OPEX
Average avoided energy costs by discharging
Internal energy change
Auxiliary power consumption
Specific TES CAPEX
Annual DH System OPEX
Efficiency of the post heating unit(s)

TABLE 17: LIST OF RELEVANT KDPs FOR THE DESIGN PHASE.

KDP
Installed capacity of the heat production units MW _{th}
Design storage capacity
Maturity of the technologies used
Maturity of the solution

No major points are observed that motivate discussion.

On the bottom of our KI evaluation list, with an average score below or equal to 2,5 we got the following KIs,

TABLE 18: LIST OF LESS RELEVANT KPIS FOR THE DESIGN PHASE.

KPI
Seasonal energy efficiency
Heat losses of the DHN
Levelized cost of energy storage (LCOES) *Simplified or detailed
Number of volume storage cycles per year
MIX number
Exergy related KPIS, e.g. Exergy efficiency

TABLE 19: LIST OF LESS RELEVANT KDPs FOR THE DESIGN PHASE.

KDP
Installed consumers capacity in MW _{th}
Design energy density

This is almost the same list that resulted from the opportunity phase rating, with the difference that the following KPIS are not listed here anymore; “Internal energy change”, “Efficiency of the post heating unit(s)” and “auxiliary power consumption”. Notice that all the missing KPIS, i.e. KPIS that gain relevance, are related to the operation of the TES System.

The already discussed discrepancy for the KPI “Seasonal energy efficiency” is still present.

Finally, it is relevant to mention that in both project phases, opportunity, and design phase, the KPIS “MIX number” and “Exergy related KPIS, e.g. Exergy efficiency” are evaluated with a low score. However, KPIS related to the storage temperature such as “Min/max temperature for the discharge” and “Min/max return temperature - to the storage” are regarded as relevant, especially for the design phase. The storage temperatures are clearly influenced by the mixing within the TES and remain a very important topic worth to evaluate and analyze. It is interpreted that the demo partners have 1) more interest on the effective result of mixing on the temperatures rather than on the details of the mixing degree and prefer 2) to use KPIS that are widely used and more straightforward to obtain. It can be said that the KPIS related to mixing (e.g. MIX number and exergy related KPIS) are rather used for detailed analysis for R&D purposes by either researchers or manufacturers and rarely used in the context of system simulations neither for the evaluation of existing TES, as monitoring equipment is often limited to a few sensors at different highs for the purpose of assessment of the TES energy content and TES management rather than to analyze mixing within the TES.

4. Conclusion

Besides the lists of KIs ordered by relevance for the three project phases considered (opportunity, design and operation), several insights can be drawn from the analysis, particularly regarding the importance of the KPIS and KDPs in the “opportunity” and “design” project phases. These are summarized below,

- The opportunity phase does focus on KDPs to track aspects that strongly constrain the design and feasibility of the project (e.g. space available, DHN temperatures, ...) as well as a few key economic KPIS such as TES (and TES system) investment and LCOH (TES system and DH). The relevant data for these KPIS, such as charged/discharged heat (amount and cost), is also

crucial. The relevance of these KPIs, especially regarding how much the existing DH system is considered, varies between project partners and specific projects and therefore needs to be concretized individually. This depends mainly on 1) the level of interaction between the TES system being designed and the existing system (e.g. is the TES system charged by the DHN? Will it support the existing system or take over a large part of heat production?), and 2) the technologies being considered and goals/requirements for the project (e.g. is the share of renewables sources like solar thermal high, are low OPEX expected? Are the needs for land high?)

- In the design phase, the number of relevant KPIs and specially KDPs increases, reflecting the need for more detailed specifications as the project progresses and becomes more defined. These KPIs and KDPs are considered to optimize the system design (e.g. storage height, lifetime, ...) and operation (e.g. min/max temperature for the discharge, charge/discharge capacities, ...). They also consider the impact on TES performance (e.g. TES efficiency) and the overall DH system (e.g. energy source mix of the overall system).

A visual sketch of these summary is given in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2: ROUGH SKETCH OF KDPs AND KPIs USE ON THE OPPORTUNITY AND DESIGN PHASE OF AN LTES PROJECT.

All in all, the evaluation gives a good overview on the main relevant aspects for the two project phases Opportunity and Design, providing a cluster of relevant (and not relevant) KIs and providing some insights through direct discussions. However, obtaining more detailed conclusions from the KI assessment is challenging due to the simplicity of the method used.

Annex A: Description of KPIs and KDPs

FIGURE 3: SCHEMATIC OF DH ENERGY SYSTEM AND BOUNDARIES (INDICATED WITH COLOURED BOXES) USED FOR THE CATEGORIZATION OF KPIs AND KDPs.

TABLE 20: LIST OF KPIS AND KDPs CONSIDERED IN THIS STUDY AND THEIR DESCRIPTION.

Symbol and/or formula	Description (proposal from bibliography)	KPI / KDP	KPI/KDP type	System boundary
H	Height or depth of the storage. Important design parameter regarding regulation (the drilling depth can be given as an additional information, if different)	Storage height / depth	Technical KDP	Component TES
Slope	Slope of the storage (applicable to PTES).	Storage slope	Technical KDP	Component TES
A_{Land}	Area required for subsystem (storage + additional components. E.g. solar thermal energy system, boiler house, ...) in e.g. m ² .	Land required	Technical/Environmental KDP	Component TES
T_{max} and T_{min}	T_{max} is the maximum temperature reachable within the storage, T_{min} is the minimum temperature reachable within the storage	Design storage temperature range	Technical KDP	Component TES
$Q_{st} = (T_{max} - T_{min}) \cdot Cp \cdot V$	Defines the energy storable in the system and depends on the storage process, the medium and the size of the system Q_{st} : Storage capacity V: Storage volume T_{max} : Maximum temperature reachable within the storage T_{min} : Minimum temperature reachable within the storage Cp: Specific heat capacity	Design storage capacity	Technical KDP	Component TES
$E_{st} = Q_{st} / A$ or Q_{st}/VWE	Storage capacity related to volume or area occupied by the storage where: Q_{st} : Storage capacity VWE: Storage water equivalent volume (= storage volume if water is the medium) A: Area required	Design energy density	Technical KDP	Component TES
	Referred to technical lifetime, i.e. time span during which the TES can be operated without need of major re-investments to e.g. repair, rebuild parts of the system.	Storage lifetime	Technical KDP	Component TES
	The maturity of the technologies used can be evaluated with help of e.g. technology readiness factor (TRL)	Maturity of the technologies used	Technical KDP	TES system
	The novelty and associated risks of the project can be evaluated based on inhouse experience and/or at world level (number of same/similar projects already done)	Maturity of the solution	Technical KDP	TES system
	Distance between Subsystem and connection to the DHN in e.g. meters	Distance to DHN	Technical KDP	TES system
$(M_{str} - M_{exp}) / (M_{str} - M_{mix})$	M_{exp} : energy momentum of the experimental tank. M_{mix} : energy momentum of an entirely mixed tank with the same amount of energy than the experimental tank. M_{str} : energy momentum of a perfectly stratified tank with the same amount of energy than the experimental tank. The MIX number has no dimension and is between 0 (tank perfectly stratified) and 1 (tank completely mixed). This indicator measures the distribution of the temperature inside the tank.	MIX number	Technical KPI	Component TES
Exergy efficiency = Ex_{out}/Ex_{in}	Ex_{in} is the exergy entering the system: $\int_{dis} (1 - T_0/T_{dis,out}) dE$ Ex_{out} is the exergy exiting the system: $\int_{cha} (1 - T_0/T_{cha,in}) dE$ Unlike energy efficiency, exergy efficiency also accounts for the level of stratification, as mixing reduces the exergy content.	Exergy related KPIs, e.g. Exergy efficiency	Technical KPI	Component TES
	Temperature range dischargeable from the storage (can be different from charging temperature for a BTES or an ATEs for instance)	Min/max temperature for the discharge	Technical KPI	Component TES
$T_{max,m}$ and $T_{min,m}$	Return temperature range entering the storage	Min/max return temperature (to the storage)	Technical KPI	Component TES
	Discharge and charge capacity of the subsystem in either MW _{th} or m ³ /h	Charge and discharge capacity (Max or averaged e.g. annually)	Technical KPI	Component TES
$E_{cha} = \int_{yr} mflow_{cha} \cdot cp \cdot (T_{in} - T_{out})$	Heat charged into the storage in a year $mflow_{cha}$ is the mass flow going in the storage when charging T_{in} and T_{out} are the temperatures of the flows going in and out of the storage	Annual charged heat	Technical KPI	Component TES
$E_{dis} = \int_{yr} mflow_{dis} \cdot cp \cdot (T_{out} - T_{in})$	Heat discharged into the storage in a year $mflow_{dis}$ is the mass flow going in the storage when charging T_{in} and T_{out} are the temperatures of the flows going in and out of the storage	Annual discharged heat	Technical KPI	Component TES
$\Delta E_{st} = E_{end} - E_{start}$	E_{end} and E_{start} are the respectively the energy content of the storage at the end and the start of the considered period	Internal energy change	Technical KPI	Component TES
$E_{loss} = E_{cha} - E_{dis} - \Delta E_{st}$	E_{loss} = Energy lost, E_{cha} = Charged energy; E_{dis} = Discharged energy; ΔE_{st} = Change in the internal energy of the storage system	Storage losses	Technical KPI	Component TES
$\eta_1 = E_{dis} / (E_{cha} - \Delta E_{st})$ or $\eta_2 = (E_{dis} + \Delta E_{st}) / E_{cha}$	E_{cha} = Charged energy; E_{dis} = Discharged energy; ΔE_{st} = Change in the internal energy of the storage system	TES Energy efficiency	Technical KPI	Component TES
Seasonal energy efficiency = $E_{seas} / (E_{seas} + E_{loss})$	E_{loss} = Energy lost, E_{seas} is the stored seasonal energy. The stored seasonal energy can be calculated as the difference between the minimum and maximum energy content in the course of one year. Seasonal efficiency quantifies the efficiency of the storage system as if it was solely used for seasonal heat storage.	Seasonal energy efficiency	Technical KPI	Component TES

TABLE 20: LIST OF KPIS CONSIDERED IN THIS STUDY AND THEIR DESCRIPTION. (CONTINUED)

Symbol and/or formula	Description (proposal from bibliography)	KPI / KDP	KPI/KDP type	System boundary
$Ncycles_E = E_{dis,yr} / Q_{st}$	$Q_{dis,yr}$: Yearly discharged energy Q_{st} : Storage capacity	Number of heat storage cycles per year	Technical KPI	Component TES
$Ncycles_V = V_{cha,yr} / V_{st}$	$V_{cha,yr}$: Yearly volume charged (in e.g. m ³) V_{st} : Storage volume	Number of volume storage cycles per year	Technical KPI	Component TES
$E_{in,ph}$	Driving energy needed by postheating unit $E_{in,ph}$ (e.g. boiler, heat pump, ...) in MWh	Energy consumption of the Postheating unit(s)	Technical KPI	Component post heater
$\eta = E_{out} / E_{in,ph}$	Ratio useful output E_{out} (heat provided for post heating) and input $E_{in,ph}$ (e.g. electricity of a heat pump, fuel of a boiler, ...) in MWh	Efficiency of the postheating unit(s)	Technical KPI	Component post heater
	Amounts of heat produced in the DH system by each energy source (coal, gas, electricity, ...) in e.g. MWh	Energy sources mix of the overall system	Environmental KPI	DH system
	Amounts of heat produced by each technology (CHP, Heat pump, gas boiler, biomass boiler, direct P2H, ...)	Heat provided sorted by technology	Technical KPI	DH system
	Yearly to monthly heat losses of the DHN in e.g. MWh	Heat losses of the DHN	Technical KPI	DH system
	Average operating supply and return DHN temperatures	DHN Temperatures	Technical KPI	DH system
	Installed capacity of the consumers substations in MW _{th}	Installed consumers capacity in MWth	Technical KPI	DH system
	Production capacity of the heating units portfolio in MW _{th}	Installed capacity of the heat production units MWth	Technical KPI	DH system
	Value of the heat production in MWth at peak consumption.	Actual heat production peak	Technical KPI	DH system
	Electrical power consumption of the auxiliary devices needed to operate the TES system (pumps, fans, compressors, heat tracing of tanks and pipes, antifreezing heater, mixer...), if any	Auxiliary power consumption	Technical KPI	TES system
Simplified: $LCOES = TCO / (Q_s * Ncycles * lifetime)$	LCOES in EUR/kWh focused on the storage. As ratio of whole costs occurred during lifetime (Total cost of operation TCO) divided by heat supplied by LTES (heat per cycle * number of cycles per year * lifetime in years)	Levelized cost of energy storage (LCOES) *Simplified or detailed	Economic KPI	Component TES
$CAPEX_{TES}$	CAPEX of the project in EUR, refined gradually through the stages - Include Technical and non technical CAPEX (Permitting - Land acquisition - financing structuration costs)	Initial investment (TES CAPEX)	Economic KPI	Component TES
$SVC = CAPEX_{TES} / V_{WE}$	CAPEX in EUR/m ³ : the investment cost, considering the storage medium, container, and charging and discharging device V_{WE} : Water equivalent volume, i.e. water volume with equivalent heat capacity	Specific TES CAPEX	Economic KPI	Component TES
$OPEX_{TES}$	OPEX of the project in EUR/a, refined gradually through the stages - Include "Technical" and non technical (Regulatory-Administrative-etc...)	Annual TES OPEX	Economic KPI	Component TES
$OPEX_{year} = OPEX_{TES} / E_{cha-dis}$	Yearly OPEX of the project in EUR/a/MWh of heat charged or discharged. Refined gradually through the stages	Energy specific TES OPEX	Economic KPI	Component TES
$LCOH_{TES System}$	LCOH in EUR/kWh for the whole system (E.g. cost related to the thermal energy storage, the required post heating units and the "surplus" heat charged)	TES System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed	Economic KPI	TES system
$CAPEX_{TES-System}$	CAPEX of the project in EUR, refined gradually through the stages - Include Technical and non technical CAPEX (Permitting - Land acquisition - financing structuration costs)	Initial investment (TES System CAPEX)	Economic KPI	TES system
$OPEX_{TES-System}$	OPEX of the project in EUR/a, refined gradually through the stages - Include "Technical" and non technical (Regulatory-Administrative-etc...)	Annual TES System OPEX	Economic KPI	TES system
$Cost_{charging}$	Average energy cost of charging the PTES, based from various heat sources	Average energy costs of charging	Economic KPI	DH system
$Cost_{discharging}$	Average avoided energy cost by discharging from the PTES	Average avoided energy costs by discharging	Economic KPI	DH system
$LCOH_{DH System}$	LCOH in EUR/MWh for the whole DH system (E.g. cost related to the thermal energy storage, the required post heating units and the "surplus" heat charged)	DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed	Economic KPI	DH system
$OPEX_{DH System}$	OPEX of the whole DH system in EUR/a, refined gradually through the stages - Include "Technical" and non technical (Regulatory-Administrative- etc...)	Annual DH System OPEX	Economic KPI	DH system
$CO2 = \sum (i=energy sources) (CO2_{i*}E_i) / E_{tot}$	Energy specific CO2 emissions of the DH-N With : $CO2_i$ = energy specific CO2 emissions of energy source i E_i = energy produced by source i during the period considered E_{tot} = sum of E_i	Energy specific CO2 emissions with or without LTES	Environmental KPI	DH system
	General effects of LTES on surroundings. These environmental KPIS do not include a clear definition or protocol for measurement, but they are introduced in order to be highlighted in the guidelines. E.g. - Change in groundwater chemistry and quality - Changes in soil mechanics - Microbial changes - Hydrogeological effects (groundwater flow related to changes in the hydrologic equilibrium) - Acidification, eutrophication, ecotoxicity, ozone layer depletion potential	TES' effects on surroundings	Environmental KPI	TES system

Annex B: KI evaluation results

TABLE 21: KPIs AND KPIs LISTED BY RELEVANCE FOR THE OPPORTUNITY (LEFT) AND DESIGN (RIGHT) PROJECT PHASES.

Opportunity				Design			
KI	MIN	MAX	AVG	KI	MIN	MAX	AVG
Initial investment (TES CAPEX)	4,0	4,0	4,0	Land required	4,0	4,0	4,0
Initial investment (TES System CAPEX)	4,0	4,0	4,0	Storage lifetime	4,0	4,0	4,0
Annual charged heat	3,0	4,0	3,8	Annual charged heat	4,0	4,0	4,0
Annual discharged heat	3,0	4,0	3,8	Annual discharged heat	4,0	4,0	4,0
TES System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed	3,0	4,0	3,8	Storage losses	4,0	4,0	4,0
Land required	3,0	4,0	3,7	Initial investment (TES CAPEX)	4,0	4,0	4,0
Design storage temperature range	3,0	4,0	3,7	Initial investment (TES System CAPEX)	4,0	4,0	4,0
Annual TES OPEX	2,0	4,0	3,7	TES' effects on surroundings	4,0	4,0	4,0
Average energy costs of charging	3,0	4,0	3,6	Storage height / depth	3,0	4,0	3,8
Storage losses	3,0	4,0	3,5	Storage slope	3,0	4,0	3,8
DHN Temperatures	3,0	4,0	3,5	Charge and discharge capacity (Max or averaged e.g. annually)	3,0	4,0	3,8
Annual TES System OPEX	2,0	4,0	3,5	Energy consumption of the Postheating unit(s)	3,0	4,0	3,8
DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed	1,0	4,0	3,5	Energy sources mix of the overall system	3,0	4,0	3,8
Storage lifetime	3,0	4,0	3,3	TES System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed	3,0	4,0	3,8
Number of heat storage cycles per year	3,0	4,0	3,3	Design storage temperature range	3,0	4,0	3,7
Energy consumption of the Postheating unit(s)	3,0	4,0	3,3	Distance to DHN	3,0	4,0	3,7
Energy sources mix of the overall system	3,0	4,0	3,3	TES Energy efficiency	3,0	4,0	3,7
Design storage capacity	2,0	4,0	3,3	DHN Temperatures	3,0	4,0	3,7
Storage height / depth	3,0	4,0	3,2	Heat provided sorted by technology	2,0	4,0	3,7
Charge and discharge capacity (Max or averaged e.g. annually)	3,0	4,0	3,2	Annual TES OPEX	2,0	4,0	3,7
Energy specific CO2 emissions with or without LTES	3,0	4,0	3,2	Annual TES System OPEX	2,0	4,0	3,7
Maturity of the solution	2,0	4,0	3,2	Average energy costs of charging	3,0	4,0	3,6
Distance to DHN	2,0	4,0	3,2	Min/max temperature for the discharge	2,0	4,0	3,5
TES Energy efficiency	2,0	4,0	3,2	Min/max return temperature (to the storage)	2,0	4,0	3,5
Heat provided sorted by technology	2,0	4,0	3,2	Actual heat production peak	2,0	4,0	3,5
Specific TES CAPEX	2,0	4,0	3,2	DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed	1,0	4,0	3,5

TABLE 21 (CONTINUATION): KPIs AND KPIs LISTED BY RELEVANCE FOR THE OPPORTUNITY (LEFT) AND DESIGN (RIGHT) PROJECT PHASES.

Opportunity				Design			
KI	MIN	MAX	AVG	KI	MIN	MAX	AVG
Min/max temperature for the discharge	2,0	4,0	3,0	Number of heat storage cycles per year	3,0	4,0	3,3
Min/max return temperature (to the storage)	2,0	4,0	3,0	Installed capacity of the heat production units MWth	2,0	4,0	3,3
Installed capacity of the heat production units MWth	2,0	4,0	3,0	Energy specific CO2 emissions with or without LTES	3,0	4,0	3,2
Actual heat production peak	2,0	4,0	3,0	Energy specific TES OPEX	2,0	4,0	3,2
Energy specific TES OPEX	2,0	4,0	3,0	Average avoided energy costs by discharging	2,0	4,0	3,2
Average avoided energy costs by discharging	2,0	4,0	3,0	Design storage capacity	2,0	4,0	3,0
Maturity of the technologies used	1,0	4,0	3,0	Internal energy change	2,0	4,0	3,0
TES' effects on surroundings	1,0	4,0	3,0	Auxiliary power consumption	2,0	4,0	3,0
Annual DH System OPEX	1,0	4,0	2,8	Specific TES CAPEX	2,0	4,0	3,0
Storage slope	2,0	3,0	2,7	Annual DH System OPEX	2,0	4,0	3,0
Internal energy change	2,0	3,0	2,5	Maturity of the technologies used	1,0	4,0	3,0
Efficiency of the postheating unit(s)	2,0	3,0	2,5	Maturity of the solution	2,0	4,0	2,8
Auxiliary power consumption	1,0	3,0	2,3	Efficiency of the postheating unit(s)	2,0	4,0	2,8
Seasonal energy efficiency	1,0	4,0	2,2	Seasonal energy efficiency	1,0	4,0	2,5
Installed consumers capacity in MWth	1,0	3,0	2,0	Installed consumers capacity in MWth	1,0	3,0	2,3
Design energy density	1,0	3,0	1,7	Heat losses of the DHN	1,0	3,0	1,8
Heat losses of the DHN	1,0	2,0	1,5	Design energy density	1,0	3,0	1,7
Levelized cost of energy storage (LCOES) *Simplified or detailed	1,0	2,0	1,5	Levelized cost of energy storage (LCOES) *Simplified or detailed	1,0	3,0	1,7
Number of volume storage cycles per year	1,0	2,0	1,3	Number of volume storage cycles per year	1,0	2,0	1,3
MIX number	0,0	1,0	0,7	MIX number	1,0	2,0	1,2
Exergy related KPIs, e.g. Exergy efficiency	0,0	1,0	0,7	Exergy related KPIs, e.g. Exergy efficiency	1,0	2,0	1,2

TABLE 22: KPIs AND KPIs LISTED BY RELEVANCE FOR THE OPERATION PROJECT PHASE.

Operation			
KI	MIN	MAX	AVG
Charge and discharge capacity (Max or averaged e.g. annually)	4,0	4,0	4,0
Annual charged heat	4,0	4,0	4,0
Annual discharged heat	4,0	4,0	4,0
Energy consumption of the Postheating unit(s)	4,0	4,0	4,0
Storage lifetime	3,0	4,0	3,8
Min/max temperature for the discharge	3,0	4,0	3,8
Min/max return temperature (to the storage)	3,0	4,0	3,8
TES Energy efficiency	3,0	4,0	3,8
Energy sources mix of the overall system	3,0	4,0	3,8
Storage losses	3,0	4,0	3,7
DHN Temperatures	3,0	4,0	3,7
TES System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed	3,0	4,0	3,7

TABLE 22 (CONTINUATION): KPIs AND KPIS LISTED BY RELEVANCE FOR THE OPERATION PROJECT PHASE.

Operation			
KI	MIN	MAX	AVG
Heat provided sorted by technology	2,0	4,0	3,7
TES' effects on surroundings	2,0	4,0	3,7
Average energy costs of charging	3,0	4,0	3,6
Design storage temperature range	3,0	4,0	3,3
Number of heat storage cycles per year	3,0	4,0	3,3
Internal energy change	2,0	4,0	3,3
Actual heat production peak	2,0	4,0	3,3
DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed	1,0	4,0	3,3
Annual TES OPEX	0,0	4,0	3,3
Annual TES System OPEX	0,0	4,0	3,3
Initial investment (TES System CAPEX)	0,0	4,0	3,2
Installed capacity of the heat production units MWth	2,0	4,0	3,2
Energy specific TES OPEX	2,0	4,0	3,2
Average avoided energy costs by discharging	2,0	4,0	3,2
Annual DH System OPEX	2,0	4,0	3,0
Initial investment (TES CAPEX)	0,0	4,0	3,0
Energy specific CO2 emissions with or without LTES	3,0	3,0	3,0
Design storage capacity	2,0	4,0	2,8
Efficiency of the postheating unit(s)	2,0	4,0	2,8
Auxiliary power consumption	2,0	4,0	2,7
Seasonal energy efficiency	1,0	4,0	2,3
Installed consumers capacity in MWth	1,0	3,0	2,2
Specific TES CAPEX	0,0	4,0	2,0
Heat losses of the DHN	1,0	3,0	1,8
Maturity of the solution	0,0	3,0	1,8
Levelized cost of energy storage (LCOES) *Simplified or detailed	1,0	3,0	1,7
Maturity of the technologies used	0,0	3,0	1,7
Distance to DHN	0,0	4,0	1,6
Storage height / depth	0,0	4,0	1,5
Storage slope	0,0	4,0	1,5
Land required	0,0	4,0	1,5
MIX number	1,0	2,0	1,5
Number of volume storage cycles per year	1,0	2,0	1,3
Exergy related KPIs, e.g. Exergy efficiency	1,0	2,0	1,2
Design energy density	0,0	2,0	0,8

TABLE 23: EVALUATION BY EACH DEMO-TEAM OF KPIS AND KDPs FOR THE OPPORTUNITY PHASE. KIs LISTED BY RELEVANCE.

Rostock (DE)	Pau (FR)	Pancevo (RS)	Wien (AT)	Choszczno (PL)	Hechingen (DE)	KI
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Initial investment (TES CAPEX)
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Initial investment (TES System CAPEX)
4,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Annual charged heat
4,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Annual discharged heat
4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	TES System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed
4,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	Land required
4,0	3,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	Design storage temperature range
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	Annual TES OPEX
3,0	3,0		4,0	4,0	4,0	Average energy costs of charging
4,0	4,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	Storage losses
4,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	DHN Temperatures
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	2,0	Annual TES System OPEX
4,0	4,0	1,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed
4,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	3,0	Storage lifetime
4,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	3,0	Number of heat storage cycles per year
4,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	Energy consumption of the Postheating unit(s)
4,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	Energy sources mix of the overall system
4,0	3,0	2,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	Design storage capacity
4,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	Storage height / depth
4,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	Charge and discharge capacity (Max or averaged e.g. annually)
3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	3,0	Energy specific CO2 emissions with or without LTES
4,0	3,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	Maturity of the solution
4,0	2,0	3,0	4,0	3,0	3,0	Distance to DHN
4,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	TES Energy efficiency
4,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	Heat provided sorted by technology
2,0	2,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	Specific TES CAPEX
4,0	3,0	3,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	Min/max temperature for the discharge
4,0	2,0	3,0	2,0	3,0	4,0	Min/max return temperature (to the storage)
4,0	2,0	4,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	Installed capacity of the heat production units MWth
4,0	2,0	4,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	Actual heat production peak
3,0	2,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	3,0	Energy specific TES OPEX
3,0	3,0	2,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	Average avoided energy costs by discharging
4,0	4,0	1,0	3,0	2,0	4,0	Maturity of the technologies used
3,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	1,0	3,0	TES' effects on surroundings
4,0	3,0	1,0	4,0	3,0	2,0	Annual DH System OPEX
3,0	2,0	3,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	Storage slope
3,0	2,0	2,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	Internal energy change
3,0	2,0	3,0	2,0	3,0	2,0	Efficiency of the postheating unit(s)
3,0	3,0	3,0	1,0	2,0	2,0	Auxiliary power consumption
2,0	1,0	3,0	4,0	2,0	1,0	Seasonal energy efficiency
3,0	2,0	2,0	1,0	2,0	2,0	Installed consumers capacity in MWth
1,0	1,0	1,0	3,0	3,0	1,0	Design energy density
2,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	2,0	2,0	Heat losses of the DHN
2,0	1,0	1,0	2,0	2,0	1,0	Levelized cost of energy storage (LCOES) *Simplified or detailed
2,0	1,0	1,0	2,0	1,0	1,0	Number of volume storage cycles per year
1,0	1,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	1,0	MIX number
1,0	1,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	1,0	Exergy related KPIS, e.g. Exergy efficiency

TABLE 24: EVALUATION BY EACH DEMO-TEAM OF KPIS AND KDPs FOR THE DESIGN PHASE. KIs LISTED BY RELEVANCE.

Rostock (DE)	Pau (FR)	Pancevo (RS)	Wien (AT)	Choszczno (PL)	Hechingen (DE)	KI
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Land required
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Storage lifetime
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Annual charged heat
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Annual discharged heat
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Storage losses
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Initial investment (TES CAPEX)
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Initial investment (TES System CAPEX)
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	TES' effects on surroundings
4,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	Storage height / depth
4,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	Storage slope
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	Charge and discharge capacity (Max or averaged e.g. annually)
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	Energy consumption of the Postheating unit(s)
4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Energy sources mix of the overall system
4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	TES System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed
4,0	3,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	Design storage temperature range
3,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	Distance to DHN
4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	TES Energy efficiency
4,0	3,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	DHN Temperatures
4,0	2,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	Heat provided sorted by technology
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	Annual TES OPEX
4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	Annual TES System OPEX
3,0	3,0		4,0	4,0	4,0	Average energy costs of charging
4,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	3,0	4,0	Min/max temperature for the discharge
4,0	3,0	4,0	2,0	4,0	4,0	Min/max return temperature (to the storage)
4,0	3,0	4,0	2,0	4,0	4,0	Actual heat production peak
4,0	4,0	1,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	DH System levelized cost of heat (LCOH) *Simplified or detailed
3,0	3,0	4,0	3,0	4,0	3,0	Number of heat storage cycles per year
4,0	2,0	4,0	2,0	4,0	4,0	Installed capacity of the heat production units MWth
3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	3,0	Energy specific CO2 emissions with or without LTES
2,0	2,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	Energy specific TES OPEX
3,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	Average avoided energy costs by discharging
3,0	2,0	2,0	3,0	4,0	4,0	Design storage capacity
3,0	3,0	3,0	2,0	4,0	3,0	Internal energy change
3,0	3,0	4,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	Auxiliary power consumption
2,0	2,0	4,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	Specific TES CAPEX
3,0	3,0	2,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	Annual DH System OPEX
3,0	4,0	1,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	Maturity of the technologies used
3,0	3,0	2,0	3,0	2,0	4,0	Maturity of the solution
3,0	2,0	4,0	3,0	3,0	2,0	Efficiency of the postheating unit(s)
2,0	1,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	1,0	Seasonal energy efficiency
3,0	2,0	3,0	1,0	3,0	2,0	Installed consumers capacity in MWth
3,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	3,0	2,0	Heat losses of the DHN
1,0	1,0	1,0	3,0	3,0	1,0	Design energy density
2,0	1,0	1,0	2,0	3,0	1,0	Levelized cost of energy storage (LCOES) *Simplified or detailed
1,0	1,0	1,0	2,0	2,0	1,0	Number of volume storage cycles per year
1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	2,0	MIX number
1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	2,0	1,0	Exergy related KPIS, e.g. Exergy efficiency

